

BIOMASS CONVERTIBILITY AND ENERGY SECURITY IN INDIA

Dr. Krishna Kant Sharma¹

ABSTRACT:

The purpose of this study was to examine the energy vulnerability, insecurity in India and the manner biomass can ensure country's energy security. Various emerging empirical data and information are put forward regarding convertibility, availability, affordability, and utility of biomass energy. The study had further investigated the relationship of energy security with the energy policy, developmental needs, economy, solid waste management, greenhouse & climate change issues, energy cropping, plantation, and technology.

The study is suitable for the both policy bodies and the society as it would provide emerging information on the biomass a safe and sustainable source of energy. Policy bodies in India would realize that more and more use of biomass is essential for energy security of India. India should try to meet as much energy requirement from the biomass. Policy bodies required to work on the convertibility issues because the availability of the biomass is tremendous in this country. India can go for energy crops and plantations for energy security.

A mixed and interdisciplinary approach was adopted for this research, including literature survey and review, case studies, interviews with energy experts, and one workshop.

Key words: *Energy Security; Biomass; Biomass Energy Convertibility; Biomass Renewable Energy*

¹¹ Working as teacher and head of Department KPS College, Nadwan (Patliputra University, Patna); Mobile: 9504782781; Email: kksharma69@yahoo.com.

INTRODUCTION:

The study aimed to collect and put forward emerging scientific and empirical data on energy insecurity and vulnerability in India and the manner it may be addressed by harnessing the potential of biomass. Until 1980s, biomass was the major source of energy for various domestic, cottage, and industrial needs. However, use of biomass was demotivated terming it unfriendly to the environment and a sign of backwardness by the so called developed mentalists. As a result, most of the urban households and small scale industries started using fossil fuels, gas, and electricity, which was comparatively costlier and now there are evidences that they are more hazardous for the environment.

As a matter of policy, biomass was still not as preferred as a major source of renewable energy (RE), whereas, most developed countries have put their focus on the biomass. No adequate research was done to develop adequate technologies and biomass burner for a safe source of energy for households, cottage, and minor industries. Almost 200 million households use gas as a source of energy for cooking in India. As a matter of policy there is virtually no role for biomass in maintaining energy security in India. The energy policy of India is largely defined by the country's expanding energy deficit and

increased focus on developing alternative sources of energy particularly nuclear, solar, and wind energy. Whereas, biomass were a good source of renewable energy.

Biomass is plant or animal material used for energy production (electricity or heat), or in various industrial processes as raw material for a range of products (Rehman, Mushtaq, Zahoor, Jamil, & Murtaza, 2015). Burning plant-derived biomass releases CO₂, but it has still been classified as a renewable energy source in the EU and UN legal frameworks because photosynthesis cycles the CO₂ back into new crops. In some cases, this recycling of CO₂ from plants to the atmosphere and back into plants can even be CO₂ negative, as a relatively large portion of the CO₂ is moved into the soil during each cycle. Cofiring with biomass has increased in coal power plants, because it makes it possible to release less CO₂ without the cost associated with building new infrastructure. Co-firing is not without issues however, often an upgrade of the biomass has been the beneficiary. Upgrading to higher grade fuels can be achieved by different methods, broadly classified as thermal, chemical, or biochemical.

The animal and plant kingdoms are mutually interdependent and are the source of biomass. Plant kingdom provides food, oxygen, and biomass.

Traditionally, biomass has been used as a source of energy in every human civilization. However, in the 20th century the same was not as preferred because of vested economic interests. A propaganda was spread that use of biomass as energy is unsafe and a sign of backwardness. Using gas, fossil fuels, and other source of energy was considered necessary for development. The International Human Development Index also preferred use of gas, fossil fuels, and other sources of energy. It was deliberately done even being fully aware that a developing country like India would be not so capable of ensuring expenditure on other renewable energy sources. Certainly, a role was and has and still being played by the international political economists.

Now recent research has found that using biomass as an energy source can be a better solution compared to all other sources including fossil fuels, gas, and electricity. However, the same is so far neglected in Indian energy policies.

The large amount of solid wastes including biomass produced in rural areas, demanded adequate solid waste disposal and one aspect of it can be their use as a safe source of energy. In rural areas energy security could be highly linked to solid waste disposal, however, this issue has never been studied properly. India is striding ahead with its energy security, however, it would be unwise to ignore the traditional use of biomass as an energy source.

Use of biomass can be more environmentally friendly compared to fossil fuels and various gases. In the name of reducing carbon emission we cannot promote of imports of fossil fuels and gases because can damage our public exchequer. Now scientific studies have shown that use of coal and biomass, which are found abundantly in India is environmentally safer than fossil fuel and gases. Therefore, using coal and biomass as a safe source of energy could be equally good for energy security and solid waste disposal. Traditionally, in India coal was converted to its form of which is generically refereed as gul. However, in the name of convenience, use of gas has largely replaced the use of gul and other biomass in urban areas and same is being replicated in the rural areas. In addition, it is required to get rid of the notion that use of fossil fuel and gas is not a sign of development, and use of coal and biomass and coal is a sign of backwardness. In the name of climate change, our governments came under pressure and decided to import fuels, neglecting the use of coal and biomass. There were numerous gul manufacturing units at local levels, which have almost shut down as people preferred fossil fuels, gas, and electricity.

A study has found that India's energy demand is growing at 4 per cent annually, and is expected to double, from 700 million tonnes of oil equivalent (MTOE) in 2010 to 1,500 MTOE by 2030. Even there is no any specific mention of biomass as a conventional source of energy in *Niti Ayog* energy documents. Any household cannot depend on any

one source of energy and there must be multiple options. Solar and wind energy cannot be a dependable substitute for biomass in cooking in many rural areas. Guided and supervised combustion of biomass needed to be promoted by the government by proving advanced technologies.

The world is moving away from overwhelming dependence on fossil fuel, and within the fossil fuels, away from coal and oil in favor of gas. Against an 88 percent total share of fossil fuels globally in the primary energy mix in the year 2005, the same fell to 86 percent in the year 2015. The share of oil in particular has fallen from 36 percent to 33 percent, while that of natural gas has increased from 23 percent to 24 percent, and that of Renewable Energy (including nuclear and large hydro) has gone up from 12.5 percent to 14 percent in the period 2005-15. The above trends, principally owing to climate change concerns, are expected to be maintained over the medium term.

The success of horizontal drilling combined with the technology of hydraulic fracture, has come to be established in the US where the production of natural gas went up from 511 BCM in 2005 to 767 BCM in 2015. This has boosted the already rising production of natural gas in the world from 2791 BCM in 2005 to 3539 BCM in the year 2015. As the price of gas is lower than that of oil, and is also one-third lesser as carbon emitting than oil, the ascendancy of gas vis-a-vis oil is likely to continue in the near foreseeable future.

Due to multiple reasons, including the two factors listed above, along with other commodity prices, oil and gas prices have softened, and this is triggering energy policy reforms across the world. The prices of oil and gas have fallen by 50 percent and 70 percent, respectively over 2014. Many oil importing countries, including India, have been able to attempt bold petroleum pricing reforms, and are in a sound fiscal position to attempt larger energy policy reforms. Maturity of renewable energy technologies The sharp decline in the prices of wind and solar technologies in the recent years by about 60 percent and 52 percent respectively between 2010 and 2015 (in kWh terms), has led to a change in the relative importance of energy sources. Tropical countries, including India, are richly endowed with the above resources, and can harness them in an innovative manner to meet energy requirements at decentralized locations. Recently, solar and wind energy prices have achieved bus bar grid parity at the generation end.

The adverse effects of climate change are much more discernible than ever before, with a better understanding of the relationship between energy use and poor environmental outcomes. While the global agenda is of common concern, there is a heightened consciousness of the need to fix poor air quality standards in Indian cities, which is being reflected in tough administrative actions and court mandated orders.

Biomass is regarded as a most important renewable source of energy because it can be used as an alternative source for energy production. Natural sources for energy production are becoming extinct day by day. The main reason behind the biomass energy production is that it can be produced from wood, plant and animal wastes, forestry wastes which indicate that biomass can be produced from those materials that are regarded as wasted materials which are again re-used and energy is produced. Biomass do not emit any harmful gases, produces clean energy, abundant and renewable, and reduces the usage of fossil fuels for energy production and also it can be used to create different products. The main reason behind biomass usage is it reduces emissions of greenhouse gases. Usage of biomass will grow within the coming years.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Biomass is a safe source of energy, it reduces greenhouse gases, widely and cheaply available (Our Energy, 2019). Likewise, fossil fuels a biomass based power plants can raise similar, but not identical, concerns about air emissions and water use, however, the feedstock of biomass plants can be sustainable produced, while fossil fuels are non-renewable. Even the sources of biomass resources for producing electricity are diverse; including energy crops (like switch grass), agricultural waste, manure, forest products and waste, and urban waste (UCS USA, 2019).

India ranks at 81 position in overall energy self-sufficiency at 66 percent in 2014 (Wikipedia, 2016). Rural area of Greece, use mixed Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) and biomass as energy (Rentizelas, Tolis, & Tatsiopoulos, 2014). Biomass and biofuels made from biomass are alternative energy sources to fossil fuels—coal, petroleum, and natural gas. Burning either fossil fuels or biomass releases carbon dioxide (CO₂), a greenhouse gas. However, the plants that are the source of biomass capture a nearly equivalent amount of CO₂ through photosynthesis while they are growing, which can make biomass a carbon-neutral energy source (EIA, 2019). In a study it was found that biomass can be purposely grown as energy crops (miscanthus, switchgrass), wood or forest residues, waste from food crops (wheat straw, bagasse), horticulture (yard waste), food processing (corn cobs), animal farming (manure, rich in nitrogen and phosphorus), or human waste from sewage plants (EIA, 2018). Biomass can be converted into safe energy sources using thermal, chemical, biochemical, and electrochemical methods for less environmental impacts (Wikipedia, 2019). There can be cultivation of energy crops (National Geographic, 2019). In the UK, in a study it was found that the Bioenergy use could triple to a level to 16 percent by 2032, and could play a role in getting the UK back on track with emissions reduction targets. Another report from the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) has suggested that biomass could provide 60 per cent of global renewable energy by 2030 (EST, 2019). Biomass has economic reliability, environmental reliability, and physical reliability (Lofthouse, Simmons, & Yonk, 2018). Biomass, the dry weight of living

matter, has recently attracted great interest as a fuel energy source because of its renewable nature, even though it has been used as a fuel (in the form of wood) since the earliest days of civilization. In developed countries, however, wood has been replaced by more convenient, but non-renewable energy sources such as coal, oil, natural gas and/or nuclear energy (McNulty, 1979). Biofuels derived from renewable plant biomass offer a potential carbon-neutral replacement for current liquid transportation fuels. Progress toward this initiative requires development of new methods to engineer energy crops with the desired chemical composition and physical characteristics, depolymerize lignocellulose to fermentable units, and program microbial metabolism for efficient conversion of sugars to ethanol (Chang, 2007). Biomass can make a substantial contribution to supplying future energy demand in a sustainable way. It is presently the largest global contributor of renewable energy, and has significant potential to expand into the production of heat, electricity, and fuels for transport (Bauen, et al., 2007). The International Energy Agency (IEA) predicts that biomass will become increasingly important as a source of energy, rising to 30 per cent of the world primary energy mix by 2050. In a study it was revealed that alternative subsystems such as Salix biomass, bio-recycled fertilization, and gasification technology greatly increase the overall efficiency and sustainability of the biomass energy system (Daugherty, 2001).

India's dependence on energy imports increased from 20 per cent to 33 per cent over the last 10 years, and could cross 50 per cent by 2030 on account of increasing demand and challenges in domestic production. This growing dependence has become a matter of rising concern in recent years (Sustainable Energy Foundation, 2016). The government objective should be to use of gas, renewable energy, and coal as major energy sources (Kumar, Upadhyay, & Gupta, 2017). All the Census villages are planned to be electrified by 2018, and universal electrification is to be achieved, with 24x7 electricity by 2022 (Niti Ayog, 2017). However, still the quality, regularity, and cost of electricity would be a problem. Moreover, still solid waste disposal would be a required in rural areas. There are easy methods of avoiding the emission of greenhouse gases from biomass use. Even studies have found that carbon emission from biomass is less complex than carbon emission from fossil fuel (Sharma, 2017). The same study found that even the use of gases are not so safe. Usually the reservoir of gas in the earth, plant and other celestial objects are part of creation which usually gets converted in precious metals and minerals to support the animal and plant kingdom. Therefore, the very mining of coal and other minerals are also very dangerous human activities because it would cause a damage to the sustenance of animal and plant kingdom. Animals can survive and do better only on the plant kingdom (Sharma, 2017).

A long term techno-economic analysis using the MARKAL model shows that biomass electricity technologies have significant potential to penetrate the Indian market under a fair competition with the fossil technologies. Under an

optimal greenhouse gas mitigation regime, biomass electricity penetration can reach 35 gigawatt in 2035. It is too premature to judge the effectiveness of these policies.

Biomasses are one of the most important renewable carbon-negative alternative sources of energy. Biomass derived energies are clean because biomass contains low N and S contents compared to the fossil fuels. Further, the use of biomass energy is a 'no-net' carbon emission process. Biomass energy is the one of the best ways to a sustainable energy system of the future (Ghosh, Tiwari, & Ray, 2018). Biodiesel is a cleaner burning fuel than diesel and a suitable replacement. It is made from non-toxic, biodegradable, renewable resources. Biodiesel can be produced in many ways (Murthy, 2012). The success of bagasse cogeneration is not only dependent on the choice of technology, but also on the soundness of the business model that ensures a steady revenue stream. It streamlines the sale of electricity to the utility and proposes suitable strategies to overcome the barriers (technological, institutional and financial). This revenue stream helps sugar mills to overcome inherent fluctuations in the sugar market (which has an effect on the price of sugar and the mill's bottom line) so much so that some sugar mills consider themselves to be in the business of producing electricity in which sugar is being considered only as a by-product by them (Sukumaran, 2010). Nearly 25 percent of its primary energy come from biomass resources, and close to 70 percent of rural population depend on biomass to meet their daily energy needs (Rao, 2011). With the advancement of science and knowledge, the major technological hurdles affecting biomass based CHP production can be overcome eventually. The biggest challenge for Indian biomass industry is the lack of strong driving factors, particularly energy policies and poor regulation. The potential biomass CHP technologies, achieving higher power to heat conversion ratio would be most optimal to suit Indian conditions. The geographical Bioenergy planning strategy should be developed to efficiently utilize the biomass for energy sustainability. New investments in Bioenergy business would bring manifold benefits to the environment (GHG emission savings), society (employment) and economy (new market development) (Natarajan & Pelkonen, 2015).

There were numerous national and international literatures about the use of biomass as a renewable source of energy, however, we were able to review almost 56 of them. In fact, biomass as a source of energy, especially concerning with energy security in India has not been properly studied, resulted in a lack of appropriate literature. There are no empirical and scientific data on convertibility, availability, affordability, and utility of biomass as a safe source of energy. Even there is virtually very insufficient literature of energy insecurity and vulnerability of India linking it with the international political economy, price control, rupee depreciation, and illogical scientific facts about climate change, carbon footprints, and greenhouse gases. Moreover, so far w.r.t *development* a tendency persisted among so called developed mentalists to ignore

the use of biomass. Such attitudes are not suitable for country's energy security and the overall economic security. India is very rich in biomass production, which is abundantly and cheaply available all year around. It was quite surprising that under certain vested influence India took a policy decision to rely heavily on imported oils and gases. Moreover, by harnessing solar energy also, India is getting heavily dependent on imported technologies and materials. Such decisions are not favorable to Indian economy and energy security. It was required to press a policy based upon valid information and data to harness the potential of biomass. For a better we have to increase the use of coal and biomass with improved technology. It was needed to establish that using biomass as a safe source of energy was not a sign of backwardness. However, the scenario could be changing fast and now most developed countries are considering it better for avoiding greenhouse gases and preventing the adverse effects of climate change.

It was evident that combustion of biomass produces less harmful greenhouse gases comparatively to fossil fuels and gases. The carbon compounds of biomass are less complex in nature comparatively to the fossil fuels and gases, and it easily gets assimilated into the environment supporting both the animal and plant kingdoms. In addition, there is no need to any mining or transportation activities. Therefore, it was required and suggested for the country's energy security.

The future of animal and plant kingdom lies in biomass as a safe source of energy. There are evidences that using precious gas and minerals as a source of energy would be damaging to the life of this earth planet. India's energy security lies in the maximum use of biomass as a safe source of energy. By inducing a cropping pattern change and plantation we can be self-reliant in energy. We can develop technologies for a better use of animal and plant products. In the energy sector India is not moving in the correct direction with imported sources of energy. So much so that massive efforts for producing energy and electricity using solar power cannot ensure energy security. Biomass is safe and easily available source of energy and which can reduce emissions of the greenhouse gases. Use of biomass can be equally good for both rural and urban; domestic and industrial sectors.

Biomass can be a reliable source of energy when properly utilized. Animal and woody wastes are readily available and can provide an economically viable option when used close to their sources. Biomass energy initiatives can help maintain forest health and convert methane to less harmful carbon dioxide. Government mandates and subsidies, however, can incentivize unsustainable and environmentally harmful biomass practices. While biomass may have a place in the electricity market.

Myriad economic, social, technological and institutional barriers remain to be overcome. The future prospects of biomass technologies depend considerably on removing

these barriers. The key issue before the Indian policy makers is to develop the market for biomass energy services by ensuring reliable and enhanced biomass supply, removing the tariff distortions favoring fossil fuels and producing energy services reliably with modern biomass technologies at competitive cost. Various policies, scientific, and economic aspects of using biomass has not been properly analyzed and presented.

FRAMEWORK AND METHODS:

To better understand the concept of energy security and propose workable indicators and metrics, the study relied on a four phase methodological process entailing research interview, a survey, a focused workshop, and a review of the academic literature. Start was made by conducting semi-structured research interviews with global energy security experts that would involve asking key scholars a series of open ended questions. Questions included; which dimensions of energy security are most important? What metrics, best capture these dimensions? And how might these metrics be used to create a common index or scorecard to measure national performance on energy security? Responses were sometimes captured with a digital audio recorder and always transcribed before being coded manually and synthesized. To supplement qualitative research interviews that were difficult to code, a quantitative survey instrument was used, asking experts to list important energy security dimensions and metrics. A focused, intensive, 2-3 day workshop was convened. An independent literature review was conducted looking for the key phrases “energy security”, “security of supply”, or “energy” and “security” in the titles and abstracts of articles published in Energy Policy, Energy, Electricity Journal, and The Energy Journal in the past five years.

The study puts efforts to study the current status of energy insecurity in India. Data was collected about the energy carriers and supply chains, and approaches to assess adaptive capacity and transformability.

The study used an interdisciplinary approach. Energy insecurities were studied in terms of political stability in producer countries, future reliability, international relations and upstream market. The focus would be to study the insecurity contributed by the policies, ups and downs of price in the international markets, and rupee depreciation.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

There may be a policy, however, the actions may not be according to the policy. At policy level, we needed to work towards the development of technologies leading to promotion of conversion of biomass in suitable energy for domestic, cottage, and small industries. Policy makers should realize that future of energy security lies in biomass. It is tremendously available in every nook and corner of the country and have remained the traditional source of energy which has been declared a renewable

source of energy. It can be cultivated. However, its convertibility to a suitable form of usable energy still remains an issue for which policy bodies required to apply mind. Policy makers may standards that imports, transportation, supply, and distribution of oil and gas is not a sustainable affair. They have to look for biomass as an alternative, renewable, and sustainable source of safe energy. The current policy of harnessing solar energy would also prove catastrophic in coming years. The recycling of solar panel and batteries would be a major-major problem in the coming years which is very toxic. Harnessing the nuclear energy is also not easy due to international restrictions and trade practices.

Biomass is a significant source of energy in India today, particularly in rural areas. However, most current use of firewood and agricultural residues for cooking and heating brings with it detrimental effects of indoor air pollution and associated adverse health impacts. In addition, the time spent collecting biomass fuels creates a burden on women and children, which reduces their time available for more productive activities. The availability of clean, low-cost fuels for heat and power in rural areas based on modern biomass technologies could significantly increase living standards and would be helpful in promoting rural industrialization and the generation of employment in rural areas. In addition, since sustainable use of biomass leads to no net increase in CO₂ emissions, there would be global climate benefits arising from the widespread use of biomass. This article discusses the size of the biomass resource base in India, the current status of modernized biomass technology development, and near- and midterm commercial targets for implementation of modern Bioenergy systems in India. The study would describe some advanced biomass conversion systems that might play a role in India’s energy system in the longer term. Finally, it would also describe the current barriers and constraints on increasing the penetration of modernized biomass energy in India, along with some policy suggestions for addressing these.

The national biomass policy however has a two decades of history, emanating with the rural energy policies. In mid-seventies decade, a rural energy crisis manifested as a fallout of high oil price, population growth and depletion of wood fuel resources. Import of oil was resorted to as a short-term supply-side solution. But this was unviable in the long run. India’s oil imports rose rapidly in the 1970s, rising from 8 percent of total imports in the 1970s to 24 percent in 1975 and 46 percent in 1980. High oil imports led to a growing trade deficit and balance of payment crisis. At household level, a vast section of rural poor had little disposable income to spend on commercial fuels. Policy makers perceived biomass as an energy alternative that could alleviate the crisis. The biomass strategy was multi-pronged. It focused on improving efficiency of traditional technologies, enhancing the supply of biomass, introducing modern biomass technologies to provide reliable energy services at competitive prices and

establishing institutional support. The DNES, established in 1982, implemented the program for biogas and improved cook stoves with moderate success. The programs such as fuel-wood plantation and biomass based electricity generation have begun recently. There is a growing experience of managing biomass projects. Despite some successes, the overall impact of biomass programs of the Indian energy scene is marginal. The policy perspective was too narrow and supply dominated. Biomass programs were confined to traditional applications. The market was given a little role in energy supply as well as conversion. Lately, under the economic reforms, the market oriented policies are given a greater role. The up gradation of DNES to MNES in 1992, has accorded a higher status of renewable energy technology programs. The new policies aim to promote modernization and commercialization of biomass production, combustion, densification, and electricity generation. The ninth five year plan proposes a higher support to biomass energy.

India is privileged with abundant biomass resource potentials, yet we are able to harvest small proportion because of fundamentally different deployed policies and articulated strategies. The effects of the biomass energy policies and executed strategies in India should be studied with a holistic approach. Such an approach takes the policy and strategy of the whole biomass energy sector rather than a segmented and separated sector as biofuel, biogas, biodiesel, etc. Furthermore, how they have resulted in different outcomes also needed to be addressed. The study would make India's biomass energy policy to evolve from incremental to more radical changes. It would promote within India more focus on technology development and deployment along with strong institutional creation. Therefore, in terms of biomass energy utilizations, India would demonstrate better performance.

Despite the rapid growth of commercial energy, biomass remains a principal energy source in rural and traditional sectors and contributes a third of India's energy. Technologies like biogas and improved cook stoves exist in India since half a century. The study would be helpful in ensuring India's search for new and renewable energy resources that would ensure sustainable development and energy security began in early 70's of the last century. Consequently, it would help promoting use of various renewable energy resources and efficient use of energy were identified as the two thrust areas of the sustainable development. Realizing the need for concentrated efforts in this sector, the Government of India, which has established a Commission for Additional Sources of Energy (CASE) in the Department of Science and Technology, would take suitable steps. The mandate of CASE to promote research and development activities in the field of renewable energy would be supported.

The study outcome would support the comprehensive renewable energy (RE) Policy for all-round development of the sector, encompassing all the key aspects, formulated

by the Ministry of Non-conventional Energy Sources (MNES). The study would contribute the objectives of

- Meeting the minimum energy needs through RE;
- Providing decentralized energy supply in agriculture, industry, commercial and household sectors in rural and urban areas, and
- Providing grid quality power. The policy envisages 10 percent of additional grid power Generation capacity to come from RE by 2012.

Policy initiatives of the Government of India should be further complimented to encourage the private as well as FDI, including provision of fiscal and financial incentives for a wide range of RE programs. Further, there should be procedures simplifications to ensure and provide excellent opportunities for increased investment in technology up-gradation, induction of new technologies, market development and export promotion. Foreign investors can enter into a joint venture with an Indian partner for financial and/or technical collaboration and for setting up of RE-based power generation projects.

Energy is the essence of social-ecological systems. Without a local supply human communities would be compelled to depend on distant energy production and distribution systems, which typically have significant externalities, vulnerabilities, and limits. With the global shift toward cheap fossil fuels in the 20th century, many remote communities were able to support unprecedented development. However, this development created dependencies that are now crippling communities as prices soar and supplies dwindle. Yet studies of energy in these human and natural systems remain few (Nader 2010), and there is a need to go beyond the economic and technical problems of energy supply and better analyze its social and ecological dimensions.

Before petroleum, biomass energy, particularly wood, was the most important source of energy for humankind. It remains a critical energy source for at least two billion people (Macqueen & Korhaliller, 2011). Widespread use of biomass or biofuels has been a contentious issue in different parts of the world. There are inherent advantages of using Bioenergy instead of fossil-fuels, the combustion of which results in large net CO₂ emissions. Biomass is a renewable and potentially carbon-neutral source of energy. Plants harvested sustainably for fuel can grow again, thereby sequestering carbon from the atmosphere (Lippke, Skog, Gustavsson, & Sathre, 2011). However, some studies suggest that the emissions associated with direct and indirect land-use change alone may negate the estimated climatic benefits of biofuels, particularly when they supplant carbon-rich ecosystems and displace food production (German, Schoneveld, & Pacheco, 2011) Moreover, biofuel feedstock cultivation may have implications for rural livelihoods and traditional land rights that depend on existing biomass and associated ecosystem goods and services. Therefore, more case studies are needed to

understand the complex social and environmental impacts accruing from the expansion of biomass energy.

Commercial interests, including multinational corporations, promoting fossil fuel and biofuel development often have pushed aside local indigenous peoples and ethnic minorities reliant on land resources, but lacking tenure security (Survival International, 2008) (Natcher, Hickey, Nelson, & Davis, 2009). However, what if the commercial interest is a rooted, indigenous corporation with its own forest capital?

Society needs and energy solution and security. The traditional use of biomass has gradually declined over the last few decades. Oil, gas, and electricity have become the main source of energy even in rural areas. All those are costly, not sustainable and friendly for the environment.

The social benefits of biomass are immense. It is more sustainable, renewable, and affordable than fossil fuels and gas. It truly has the capacity of reducing greenhouse gases and ensure energy security in every area of India. Biomass can provide the society a fuel diversity, which protects communities from volatile fossil fuels. Since biomass energy uses domestically-produced fuels, biomass power greatly reduces our dependence on foreign energy sources and increases national energy security. Irrational biomass burning particulates impact climate and can also affect human health when they are inhaled, causing respiratory problems. Since fires produce carbon dioxide, a major greenhouse gas, biomass burning emissions significantly influence the Earth's atmosphere and climate. Therefore, people are required to be educated about the safe and guided combustion of a biomass. A biomass is renewable, it reduces dependency on fossil fuels, doesn't produce carbon, and most importantly, it is locally, widely and cheaply available. It can cut down the transportation costs. Biomass will be available as a renewable energy source. Biomass helps climate change by reducing greenhouse gas emissions, indeed helps reduce the amount of greenhouse gas emissions that give more impact to global warming and climate change. Biomass used as a fuel reduces the need for fossil fuels for the production of heat, steam, and electricity for residential, industrial and agricultural use. It is highly suitable for rural areas and even urban areas as well. Coal, available in plenty in India can be converted to *gul*, which is a very effective source of cooking fuel. Biomass contains energy first derived from the sun: Plants absorb the sun's energy through photosynthesis, and convert carbon dioxide and water into nutrients (carbohydrates). Biomass can be burned to create heat (direct), converted into electricity (direct), or processed into biofuel (indirect).

Biomass energy has rapidly become a vital part of the global renewable energy mix and account for an ever-growing share of electric capacity added

worldwide. Renewable energy supplies around one-fifth of the final energy consumption worldwide, counting traditional biomass, large hydropower, and "new" renewables (small hydro, modern biomass, wind, solar, geothermal, and biofuels).

Traditional biomass, primarily for cooking and heating, represent about 13 percent and is growing slowly or even declining in some regions as biomass is used more efficiently or replaced by more modern energy forms. Some of the recent predictions suggest that biomass energy is likely to make up one third of the total world energy mix by 2050. In fact, biofuel provides around 3 percent of the world's fuel for transport.

The biomass energy resources are readily available in rural and urban areas of all countries. Biomass-based industries can foster rural development, provide employment opportunities and promote biomass re-growth through sustainable land management practices.

The negative aspects of traditional biomass utilization in developing countries can be mitigated by promotion of modern waste-to-energy technologies which provide solid, liquid and gaseous fuels as well as electricity. The biomass waste encompasses a wide array of materials derived from agricultural, agro-industrial, and timber residues, as well as municipal and industrial wastes.

The most common technique for producing both heat and electrical energy from biomass wastes is direct combustion. Thermal efficiencies as high as 80 – 90 percent can be achieved by advanced gasification technology with greatly reduced atmospheric emissions.

Combined heat and power (CHP) systems, ranging from small-scale technology to large grid-connected facilities, provide significantly higher efficiencies than systems that only generate electricity. Biochemical processes, like anaerobic digestion and sanitary landfills, can also produce clean energy in the form of biogas and producer gas, which can be converted to power and heat using a gas engine.

The Bioenergy systems offer significant possibilities for reducing greenhouse gas emissions due to their immense potential to replace fossil fuels in energy production. Biomass reduces emissions and enhances carbon sequestration since short-rotation crops or forests established on abandoned agricultural land accumulate carbon in the soil.

The Bioenergy usually provides an irreversible mitigating effect by reducing carbon dioxide at the source, but it may emit more carbon per unit of energy than fossil fuels unless biomass fuels are produced unsustainably.

The biomass can play a major role in reducing the reliance on fossil fuels by making use of thermochemical conversion technologies. In addition, the increased utilization of biomass-

based fuels will be instrumental in safeguarding the environment, generation of new job opportunities, sustainable development and health improvements in rural areas.

The development of efficient biomass handling technology, improvement of agro-forestry systems and establishment of small and large-scale biomass-based power plants can play a major role in rural development. Biomass energy could also aid in modernizing the agricultural economy.

When compared with wind and solar energy, biomass power plants are able to provide crucial, reliable base load generation. Biomass plants provide fuel diversity, which protects communities from volatile fossil fuels. Since biomass energy uses domestically-produced fuels, biomass power greatly reduces our dependence on foreign energy sources and increases national energy security.

A large amount of energy is expended in the cultivation and processing of crops like sugarcane, coconut, and rice, which can meet by utilizing energy-rich residues for electricity production. The integration of biomass-fueled gasifiers with coal-fired power stations would be advantageous in terms of improved flexibility in response to fluctuations in biomass availability and lower investment costs. The growth of the Bioenergy in Biomass has always been an important energy source for the country considering the benefits it offers. It is renewable, widely available, and carbon-neutral and has the potential to provide significant employment in the rural areas. Biomass is also capable of providing firm energy. About 32 percent of the total primary energy use in the country is still derived from biomass and more than 70 percent of the country's population depending upon it for its energy needs. Ministry of New and Renewable Energy has realized the potential and role of biomass energy in the Indian context and hence has initiated a number of programs for promotion of efficient technologies for its use in various sectors of the economy to ensure derivation of maximum benefits. Biomass power generation in India is an industry that attracts investments of over Rs.600 crores every year, generating more than 5000 million units of electricity and yearly employment of more than 10 million man-days in the rural areas. For efficient utilization of biomass, bagasse based cogeneration in sugar mills and biomass power generation have been taken up under biomass power and cogeneration program. Biomass power & cogeneration program would be implemented with the main objective of promoting technologies for optimum use of country's biomass resources for a grid power generation. Biomass materials used for power generation include bagasse, rice husk, straw, cotton stalk, coconut shells, soya husk, de-oiled cakes, coffee waste, jute wastes, and groundnut shells, saw dust etc.

Establishing the energy security is the need of the hour as India's energy insecurity is complimented majorly because of hostile neighborhood, supplier nations being war affected for many decades, rupee depreciation, costly transportation, and price hikes. In addition, the international political economy has also contributed the

energy insecurities largely. India is under tremendous international pressure to cut and bring down greenhouse gases. Alternatively, solar, hydrogen, and nuclear energy are being proposed in which we need heavy investments and imported technologies and materials which are not locally available. All those are major contributing factors for energy insecurities in India.

India should be a suitable, affordable, and reliable alternative and biomass can provide that required energy security for a country like India with a massive biomass production. However, people are forgetting the use of biomass for various domestic, cottage, and small industrial use. It would be difficult for such a large population to shift again towards biomass in case of emergency. Therefore, a policy is required to fulfill our major energy requirement by biomass in a sustainable manner.

Under the influence of international development and political economy, India has neglected is neglecting its rich biomass resources because of non-application of mind. This study would provide all new information and data that would help biomass to be established as a key source of renewable energy in India. Various data related to biomass utility, dependability, regularity, and convertibility would be triangulated and properly presented. The study data would help in promoting the energy cropping and plantation as well as its convertibility to electricity.

The study would help in cutting down the imports of fossil fuels and gas. India is importing precious fossil fuel and gas to meet its energy requirements, neglecting easily and cheaply available biomass that can be used as a safe energy source. Fossil fuels and gas are transported from one place to another in vehicles and underground supply pipelines, which is very costly and hazardous. In many towns pipelines are laid to supply gas in households. Whereas, biomass is part and parcel of our daily social life.

Sustainable energy innovation is at the heart of solving many of the world's toughest challenges, and is the key to tapping the full potential of energy as a contributor to the future growth and prosperity. However, despite the overall accelerating pace in recent years, innovation in the energy system is not occurring quickly and widely enough, nor is it adequately aligned, to address pressing issues and exploit new technologies to improve the lives of citizens around the world. The global energy system faces rising and shifting demands: the urgent challenge of tackling climate change and the need to expand energy access, mirrored by tremendous new opportunities created by the Fourth Industrial Revolution, which affect all sectors of the economy and society. The sustainable energy innovation challenge requires a systemic and multi stakeholder approach to help bring a broader set of nascent technologies to technical and commercial maturity. It includes a variety of perspectives and disciplines, including innovation systems, transition studies, environmental and ecological economics and policies, and

an enabling framework that aids productive interaction between system components. Energy transition is a complex process, which needs to balance the priorities of economic growth, energy security and system reliability along with environmental sustainability. This necessitates interdisciplinary perspective and collaboration between innovators, system planners, regulators, investors and end-use consumers. Governments and the private sector must improve complementary efforts and seize opportunities to cooperate in areas that can benefit from public-private collaboration and which neither governments nor businesses can solve on their own. Regulatory policies, public-funding programs and innovation alliances are key catalysts necessary to accelerate the pace of innovation. More transparency on scalable and replicable good practices of policies, programs and alliances will encourage innovation activity and large-scale integration of new technologies, solutions and business models in the energy system. Based on the review of positive examples from across different countries, the following are a few key success factors of the aforementioned catalysts: – Regulatory policies create an enabling environment for innovators, investors and consumers to participate in the new energy economy. The regulatory framework should consider aligning several instruments that reinforce the positive effects in advancing innovation in sustainable energy, including incentives for early adopters, de-risking mechanisms for investors, and compelling rationale to end-consumers for accelerated adoption. Energy policies do not work in isolation, but interact closely with other policy areas, such as trade, investment, and industrial infrastructure development. An effective policy regime with a credible agenda and long-term stability is crucial to accelerate innovation in sustainable energy.

The government should work upon few forward-looking bold ideas to achieve step-changes in the innovation process:

1. Use an institutional approach for innovation to better connect isolated groups of experts and plug the gaps that prevent faster conversion of basic research to commercially feasible projects, thus taking a longer-term view and avoiding problems of shorter political cycles.

References

- Bauen, A., Berndes, G., Bauen, M. J., Berndes, G., Londo, M., & Vuille, a. F. (2007). *Bioenergy – a Sustainable and Reliable Energy Source: A review of status and prospects*. IEA Bioenergy. Retrieved from [http://indiaenvironmentportal.org.in/files/Bioenergy_a percent20sustainable_and_reliable_energy_source.pdf](http://indiaenvironmentportal.org.in/files/Bioenergy_a_percent20sustainable_and_reliable_energy_source.pdf)
- BE Lippke, R. H., Skog, I., Gustavsson, L., & Sathre, R. (2011). Life cycle impacts of forest management and wood utilization on carbon mitigation: knowns and unknowns. *Carbon Management*, 303-333. doi:10.4155/cmt.11.24
- Chang, M. C. (2007). Harnessing energy from plant biomass. *Current Opinion in Chemical Biology*, 11(6), 677-684. doi:10.1016/j.cbpa.2007.08.039
- Daugherty, E. C. (2001). *Biomass Energy Systems Efficiency: Analyzed through a Life Cycle Assessment*. Nashville, Tennessee : Lund University.
- EIA. (2018). *Biomass Explained*. Retrieved from USA Energy Information Administration.

2. Provide information to capital-intensive innovation areas and encourage collaboration in the precompetitive stages of innovation to promote R & D investment from countries, companies and philanthropists.

3. May promote investment of public R & D grants with venture capitalists to better target grant recipients, lower administration requirements of grant applications, create collaborations between public and private capital sources and enable better timing of grant availability.

4. Provide information for co-design technology roadmaps across the public and private sector, and across borders, to improve credibility, speed up commercialization and bridge the technical and financial “valleys of death” that plague innovation.

5. Would support the mainstreaming of public procurement strategies for sustainable energy solutions, redesigning them to be forward looking, to focus on outcomes rather than specific technologies, and to offer “demand-side assistance” to early-stage innovations in areas where technology solutions do not exist.

6. May improve transparency on public R & D expenditure for sustainable energy innovation, employing existing multilateral frameworks such as Mission Innovation to facilitate better data sharing between stakeholders, and identify and better address underserved areas.

CONCLUSION

India must make a maximum use the energy source which is renewable, sustainable, and abundantly available at local levels. Biomass fulfill all those categories. The study has found that neglect of biomass and increased use of fossil fuel and gas has been under the influence of international political economy working in the energy sector. Use of imported energy is not suitable for India’s overall energy security. India should develop indigenous technology for using biomass, coal, solar, hydroelectric, and nuclear energy. However, first there would a requirement of an appropriate policy in this regard.

- EIA. (2019). *Biomass Explained: Biomass and the Environment*. Retrieved from USA Energy Information Administration: <https://www.eia.gov/energyexplained/biomass/biomass-and-the-environment.php>
- EST. (2019). *What role does biomass have to play in our energy supply?* Retrieved from Energy Saving Trust: <https://www.energysavingtrust.org.uk/blog/what-role-does-biomass-have-play-our-energy-supply>
- German, L. G., Schoneveld, C., & Pacheco, P. (2011). The social and environmental impacts of biofuel feedstock cultivation: evidence from multi-site research in the forest frontier. *Ecology and Society*, 16(3), 23. doi:10.5751/ES-04309-160324
- Ghosh, R. K., Tiwari, A., & Ray, a. D. (2018). Harnessing Biomass Energy for a Sustainable Future: A Review. *International Journal of Bioresource Science*, 5(1), 27-38. doi:10.30954/2347-9655.01.2018.3
- Kumar, H., Upadhyay, M. K., & Gupta, a. R. (2017). *Energising India: A Joint Project of the Niti Ayog of India and the Institute of Energy Economics, Japan (IEEJ)*. New Delhi: Niti Ayog of India and the Institute of Energy Economics, Japan (IEEJ).
- Lofthouse, J., Simmons, R. T., & Yonk, R. M. (2018). *Reliability of Renewable Energy: Biomass*. Retrieved from The Institute of Political Economy (IPE) at Utah State University : <https://www.usu.edu/ipe/wp-content/uploads/2015/11/Reliability-Biomass-Condensed.pdf>
- Macqueen, D., & Korhaliller, S. (2011). Bundles of energy: the case for renewable biomass energy. *Natural Resource*(24).
- McNulty, P. B. (1979). *Energy from Biomass*. doi:10.13140/2.1.3012.9444
- Murthy, S. S. (2012). Harnessing Biomass Energy for the Production of Biodiesel. *IACSIT International Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 4(3), 279-281. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/237841303_Harnessing_Biomass_Energy_for_the_Production_of_Biodiesel
- Nader, L. (2010). *he Energy Reader*. Oxford, UK: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Natarajan, K., & Pelkonen, P. (2015). *Exploiting the Unexploited Biomass Energy in India through Finnish CHP Solutions*. Joensuu, Finland : IPCBEE. doi:10.7763/IPCBEE
- Natcher, D. G., Hickey, C. G., Nelson, M., & Davis, S. (2009). Implications of tenure insecurity for Aboriginal land use in Canada. *Human Organization*, 68(3), 245-257.
- National Geographic. (2019). *Biomass Energy*. Retrieved from National Geographic: <https://www.nationalgeographic.org/encyclopedia/biomass-energy/>
- Niti Ayog. (2017). *Draft National Energy Policy*. New Delhi: Niti Ayog.
- Our Energy. (2019). *Benefits of biomass*. Retrieved from Our Energy: http://www.our-energy.com/benefits_of_biomass.html
- Rao, D. R. (2011). *Bioenergy in India: Barriers and policy options*. New Delhi: United Nations Development Programme, India. Retrieved from <http://admin.indiaenvironmentportal.org.in/files/BioenergyIndia.pdf>
- Rehman, U., Mushtaq, S., Zahoor, Z., Jamil, T., & Murtaza, a. A. (2015). Xylitol: a review on bioproduction, application, health benefits, and related safety issues. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, 55(11), 1514–28. doi:10.1080/10408398.2012.702288
- Rentizelas, A., Tolis, A., & Tatsiopoulos, a. I. (2014). Combined Municipal Solid Waste and biomass system optimization for district energy applications. *Waste Management*, 36-48. doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2013.09.026
- Sharma, K. K. (2017). Use of Biomass For Energy Security in India. *Indian Journal of Sciences and Systems*, 12-15.
- Sukumaran, K. (2010). *A road map for promotion of cogeneration in small sugar mills*. New Delhi: United Nation Development Program (UNDP).
- Survival International. (2008). *Biofuels threaten lands of 60 million tribal people*. London, UK: Survival International. Retrieved from <http://www.survivalinternational.org/news/3279>
- Sustainable Energy Foundation. (2016). *An Energy Security Index for India*. New Delhi: Shakti Sustainable Energy Foundation.
- UCS USA. (2019). *Environmental Impacts of Renewable Energy Technologies*. Retrieved from Union of Concerned Scientists; Science for a Healthy Planet and Safet World: <https://www.ucsusa.org/clean-energy/renewable-energy/environmental-impacts>
- Wikipedia. (2016). *Energy policy of India*. Wikipedia: The Free Encyclopedia.
- Wikipedia. (2019). *Biomass*. Retrieved from Wikipedia: The Free Encyclopeda: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Biomass>
